

Interpretable machine learning for cardiogram-based biometrics

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1.0 Methods and materials

To maintain readability, the full methodological description underlying the analyses, presented the block diagram (Figure 1) in the main text, is provided here in expanded form. In the Supplementary materials each step of the proposed pipeline is presented in detail, including preprocessing, delineation, feature extraction, model training, feature-importance estimation, feature-selection procedures, correlation analysis, and statistical testing across emotional states. The structure follows the order of the corresponding subsections referenced in the Results and Discussion, enabling direct cross-navigation between the body of text and the methodological elaborations provided below, which include the dataset description, preprocessing and information extraction, decision-making using machine learning, feature selection procedures, and the analysis of emotion-related effects on cardiogram-based features.

1.1 Dataset description

Our publicly available dataset is utilized for the study, comprising ECG and ICG signals recorded from 202 healthy psychology students (37 males, 163 females, and 2 who preferred not to disclose their sex/gender; mean age = 20.18 ± 1.88 years, with 9 NA for age) [1]. ECG and ICG signals are acquired simultaneously at a sampling frequency of 2000 Hz. ECG signals are recorded using Lead II electrodes placed according to the Einthoven's triangle, and ICG signals are acquired with four surface electrodes positioned on the subjects' backs. [2–4]

The recording protocol consists of two distinct parts. The initial group of 59 recordings comprises two segments, each approximately two minutes in duration: relaxation (baseline) and anger induction. The second group (143 recordings) includes three segments: baseline, neutral, and anger. A neutral phase is incorporated to control for confounding variables, such as mental engagement. Both neutral and anger-inducing fantasy materials are pre-tested in a pilot study [4]. For this study, only the baseline and anger segments are utilized. During the baseline phase, subjects were instructed to sit calmly and relax, and to optionally closing their eyes. During the anger-induction phase, participants listened to an audio-guided scenario designed to evoke anger. Detailed descriptions of the recording protocols are available in our previous publications [2,4].

1.2 Preprocessing and extraction of information of interest

This segment of analysis, which includes preprocessing and delineation steps, is adopted from our previous studies [2,3], and the scripts are available online [5]. Preprocessing and feature extraction are implemented using R programming language v4.3.0 [6], within the R Studio integrated development environment (IDE) (Posit Software, PBC, formerly RStudio, PBC).

1.2.1 Digital filtering and delineation

ECG and ICG signals are filtered using the 4th order Butterworth bandpass filter to reduce both high-frequency and low-frequency noise. The frequency bandwidth is set to 1 Hz – 40 Hz for ECG recordings and 0.5 Hz – 40 Hz for ICG recordings [7,8]. All filters are applied in a bidirectional manner to compensate for zero-phase distortion. For R peak detection, we employ the modified Pan-Tompkins algorithm [9]. The position of the peaks is double-checked automatically by verifying the location as a maximum within ± 30 ms of the detected peak, which roughly corresponds to the minimum QRS duration in healthy adults [10]. The C point is detected as the maximum value of the ICG signal occurring between two consecutive R peaks in the ECG [11,12]. To further reduce noise, ensemble averaging is conducted, which involves averaging 10 consecutive ECG and ICG beats (templates) [13]. This approach effectively minimizes noise, particularly noise with a mean value of zero (such as white noise), although it comes at the cost of reducing variability within the averaging cohort [14]. For this process, ECG and ICG templates are created with a duration of 750 ms, comprising 250 ms before the R and C peaks and 500 ms following the peaks for ECG and ICG, respectively [2,14]. A total of 9 averages is extracted per segment (baseline and anger), resulting in 18 samples per individual. The choice of nine averages is made heuristically, as it represents the maximum number of non-overlapping beats (9 averages \times 10 beats) that could be extracted from each segment while ensuring equal representation across all subjects. Besides averaging the ensemble, the RR interval and RC interval are averaged on the selected cohort, which are used as features shown in Table A1. On averaged ECG signals, we also detect the positions of Q and S points, along with T1, T, and T2 points, which represent the start, peak, and the end of the T wave, respectively [15]. Additionally, from the ICG signals, besides the C point, the B and the X points are identified, corresponding to the opening and closing of the aortic valve [11,14]. These delineation steps are adopted from our previous studies [2,3].

In line with previous studies [2,3], this study expands the analysis by using a larger number of samples per class and an extended feature set. The updated set provides broader coverage of temporal, amplitude, and morphological descriptors, with all interval-based features (except RR) normalized using Bazett's correction to reduce heart-rate-related confounding. A key enhancement is the inclusion of slope (angular) features, such as QR_slope, RS_slope, TT1_slope, TT2_slope, CB_slope, and CX_slope, which capture the rate of change in waveform segments to complement amplitudes and temporal information. The feature space is further enriched by expanded amplitude and morphological descriptors such as RT_amp and ECGQRScrest, resulting in a more comprehensive and balanced representation of ECG and ICG dynamics.

1.2.2 Fiducial-based feature extraction

The fiducial-based features represent relationships between two or more fiducial points, capturing the connections between key events in the cardiovascular system. Depending on the type of relationship, these features can be broadly categorized into temporal, amplitude, slope, and morphological features [2,13,16]. All temporal features, except for RR, are corrected using Bazett's formula to compensate for potentially high heart rate. A list of the extracted features, along with their signal of origin, domain, description, and references, is provided in Table A1. In this work, we extend prior feature sets by broadening temporal, amplitude, and morphological descriptors, and by introducing a new slope, also called angular, domain that links changes in amplitude with timing. We also develop additional temporal features that connect ECG and ICG fiducials, denoted as ECG\ICG

features. These extensions build on and generalize ideas from Patro et al. [16] and Antić et al. [3], while maintaining compatibility with established measures in the literature.

To understand the distribution of the features listed in Table A1, we calculate the Pearson and Spearman correlation coefficients with the appropriate p -value. From this analysis, we identify pairs of features with high correlation, where the absolute value of the correlation coefficient exceeds 0.7. These pairs are represented as an adjacency list, which is then interpreted as a graph structure. In this representation, features are nodes and significant correlations are edges. Groups of nodes, connected in the form of islands, are treated as clusters of highly related features. These clusters represent groups of features that share similar correlation patterns, offering a descriptive view of the structure present in the dataset. It should be noted, however, that correlation does not imply causation [17], and these clusters should be interpreted as descriptive structures rather than evidence of direct underlying mechanisms.

1.3 Decision-making

All ML model development, feature importance analysis, feature selection, and statistical testing are conducted using Python 3.9 [18], employing libraries including NumPy [19], pandas [20], matplotlib [21], pickle [18], random [18], scikit-learn [22], SciPy [23], SHAP [24], statistics [18], math [18], statmodels [25], and deap [26]. The scripts used for decision-making, feature importance analysis, and feature selection are available online [27]. In this study, we employ the RF algorithm, which demonstrated superior performance compared to other ML models in our previous research [2]. Additionally, RF inherently provides a ranked list of feature importance without requiring additional processing steps [22,28,29], making it a strong candidate for our research, as it directly supports the central aim of identifying which aspects of the ECG and ICG signals carry individual-specific information. It is important to note that hyperparameter tuning is intentionally omitted at all stages of the ML pipeline, as its computational expense is deemed excessive relative to the marginal increase in accuracy observed [2]. The focus is therefore on using ML as a benchmark to track relative changes and improve interpretability, particularly for understanding the contribution of each cardiogram to biometric identification, so the default values for hyperparameters are employed [22]. However, thorough hyperparameter tuning was performed in our previous research [1,2], in the present study, both the sample size and the feature space are substantially increased (from 8-12 up to 18 samples per individual and from 17 up to 29 extracted features), which does not guarantee that the previously optimized hyperparameters would yield the best performance under these new conditions. Moreover, prior work has shown that hyperparameter tuning in RF can indeed improve performance, but often at the cost of significant computational demand [30].

Table A1: Description of ECG, ICG, and combined ECG\ICG features, including their signal origin, domain, description, and references. Feature names reflect the fiducial points used. The suffix indicates the domain: “int” for interval (temporal), “amp” for amplitude, “slope” for slope (angular), and “crest” without a suffix denotes morphology.

Feature	Signal	Domain	Description	Reference(s)
RR_int	ECG	temporal	Heart rate	[31,32]
QRS_int	ECG	temporal	Duration of depolarization of the ventricle	[16]
T_int	ECG	temporal	Duration of repolarization of the ventricle	[15,33]
QT_int	ECG	temporal	Duration of depolarization and repolarization of the ventricle	[31]
ST_int	ECG	temporal	Duration between the end of depolarization and the end of repolarization of the ventricle	[15,16]
RQ_amp	ECG	amplitude	Amplitude difference between the R and Q points in the QRS complex	[16,31–33]
RS_amp	ECG	amplitude	Amplitude difference between the R and S points in the QRS complex	[16,31–33]

Feature	Signal	Domain	Description	Reference(s)
RT_amp	ECG	amplitude	Amplitude difference between R peak and T peak	[31]
TT1_amp	ECG	amplitude	Amplitude difference between the peak and the beginning of the T wave	[13,33]
TT2_amp	ECG	amplitude	Amplitude difference between the peak and the endpoint of the T wave	[13,33]
QR_slope	ECG	slope	Slope of QR segment	[16]
RS_slope	ECG	slope	Slope of SR segment	[16]
TT1_slope	ECG	slope	Slope between the beginning and the peak of the T wave	Inspired by [16]
TT2_slope	ECG	slope	Slope between the peak and the endpoint of the T wave	Inspired by [16]
ECGQRScrest	ECG	morphological	Crest factor of the QRS complex	Inspired by [3]
ECGTcrest	ECG	morphological	Crest factor of the T wave	[3]
BX_int	ICG	temporal	Left Ventricular Ejection Time (LVET)	[3,34]
CB_amp	ICG	amplitude	Amplitude difference between the C peak and the B point	[34]
CX_amp	ICG	amplitude	Amplitude difference between the C point and the X point	[3]
CB_slope	ICG	slope	Slope of BC segment	Inspired by [16,34]
CX_slope	ICG	slope	Slope of CX segment	Inspired by [16,34]
ICGcrest	ICG	morphological	Crest factor of BCX complex	[3]
RC_int	ECG/ICG	temporal	Duration between the peak of electrical and the peak of mechanical activity	[3]
QX_int	ECG/ICG	temporal	Duration between the onset of depolarization and the end of the mechanical activity of the ventricles	Inspired by [3,16]
QB_int	ECG/ICG	temporal	Duration between the onset of depolarization and the beginning of mechanical activity of the ventricles	Inspired by [3,16]
SX_int	ECG/ICG	temporal	Duration between the end of depolarization and the end of mechanical activity of the ventricles	Inspired by [3,16]
SB_int	ECG/ICG	temporal	Duration between the end of depolarization and the beginning of the mechanical activity of the ventricles	Inspired by [3,16]
BT_int	ECG/ICG	temporal	Duration between the peak of repolarization and the beginning of mechanical activity of the ventricles	Inspired by [3,16]
TX_int	ECG/ICG	temporal	Duration between the peak of repolarization and the end of mechanical activity of the ventricles	Inspired by [3,16]

We assume a closed-world scenario, meaning individuals not registered in the database cannot access the identification system. Consequently, the problem is designed as a multi-class (multinomial) classification task, where each individual represents a distinct class. The dataset is split into training and test sets using a 33% test set ratio with stratification. This ensures that each individual's information is proportionally represented in both the training and test datasets. RF is evaluated solely on the test set, which does not participate in the training process, using standard classification metrics, including accuracy, precision, recall, and the F1 score.

1.3.1 Feature importance

Feature importance in this study is evaluated using three complementary metrics: Gini importance (*i.e.*, reduction in impurity), permutation feature importance, and Shapley additive explanations (SHAP) [24,28,35]. In the first method, feature importance

estimation is embedded in the training process, and the importance scores are scaled so that their sum equals 1 [22,28]. This approach is computationally efficient and directly integrated into the RF training process, providing an immediate understanding of which features influence the model. In the second approach, the feature importance is evaluated using the permutation feature importance method with the n_repeat parameter set to 100 on the independent test set. Permutation-based importance is robust to features with numerous categories [36] and can be computed on an independent test set [22], ensuring a more reliable evaluation of feature relevance. On the other hand, this method is computationally more intensive, as it involves shuffling feature values multiple times and re-evaluating the model to estimate importance. As the third method, we compute SHAP values, which attribute each prediction to individual features based on cooperative game theory [24]. In the multinomial classification, SHAP produces a three-dimensional output where feature contributions are calculated for each sample and for each class, reflecting how much a given feature pushes the prediction toward or away from each possible class. To obtain a global view, these values are first averaged across classes, then converted to their absolute values and finally averaged across all samples, resulting in the mean absolute importance of each feature.

Since each of these methods captures feature importance from a different perspective, they are applied in parallel, consistent with ensemble-based strategies for feature selection [37]. As feature importance methods do not explicitly eliminate less important features, but rather provide a ranked list, we use thresholding to select only the ten highest-ranked features. The intersection of the sets is then taken, keeping only those features consistently identified among the top ten by all three methods. This strategy improves the stability of the selected features, though it comes at the expense of diversity, as unique features highlighted by a single method are excluded [37]. The resulting subset is evaluated by retraining the RF model and comparing performance against the base model that included all features. Importantly, these evaluation metrics are used solely for benchmarking the stability and informativeness of the selected feature set, and not as predictive validation in the sense of classification performance.

Assessing feature importance in datasets exhibiting multicollinearity is subject to correlation bias [35]. This arises when pairs or groups of highly correlated variables influence the importance scores assigned to individual features [35]. The analysis is conducted using clusters of highly correlated features. The collective influence of each cluster on model accuracy is assessed by randomly shuffling all features within a cluster and monitoring the resulting decrease in classification accuracy on the test set. Moreover, we examine the relationship between the Gini importance scores of individual features within and outside their respective clusters. From each cluster, a representative feature (*i.e.*, a feature that is correlated with all features in a cluster) is selected and individually shuffled to disrupt its association with the target variable. The RF model is retrained, and Gini importance scores are recalculated. The relative changes in importance scores are analyzed for highly correlated feature pairs. In contrast, the distribution of changes across all remaining features is summarized using descriptive statistics (minimum, maximum, median, the 25th percentile, and the 75th percentile).

1.4 Feature selection

In contrast to feature importance methods, which provide a ranked list of features according to their estimated significance, feature selection methods explicitly eliminate less informative features from the dataset. This approach removes the need for additional thresholding strategies to determine a final subset, since the selection process itself yields a reduced feature set along with a direct evaluation of its performance, which we validate on an independent test set. In this study, feature selection is conducted using two methods: recursive feature elimination with cross-validation (RFECV) and a genetic algorithm (GA).

RFECV starts with the complete feature set and iteratively removes the least informative features, with the number of eliminated features per step determined by a predefined parameter (commonly one). At each iteration, model performance is evaluated

using classification accuracy under cross-validation, and the process continues until the subset that yields the highest predictive performance is identified [22,28]. The minimum number of features is fixed at a predefined parameter of one, and the procedure continues by iteratively discarding the least informative feature until the optimal subset is determined [22,28].

In contrast, the GA follows a stochastic search strategy inspired by natural selection, where candidate feature subsets evolve toward optimal solutions through iterative refinement. The algorithm begins with an initial population of randomly generated subsets, and over multiple generations, applies crossover to exchange features between subsets and mutation to introduce random variations, thereby preserving diversity and reducing the risk of premature convergence. The fitness of each subset is assessed according to model performance, and the best-performing candidates are retained for subsequent iterations. In this study, the GA is implemented with a population size of 50 and evolved for 50 generations to balance exploration of the feature space with computational cost, while the crossover and mutation probabilities are set to 0.5 and 0.1, respectively, to compromise between preserving existing solutions and introducing sufficient variability to avoid premature convergence [38]. The parameters are chosen heuristically, as they are often tuned empirically based on the feature set and dataset properties.

As in the case of feature importance, the final set is produced by intersecting the features selected by both methods. The resulting consensus subset is then used to retrain the RF model, and its performance is compared with the results of the base model. Finally, the consensus feature set obtained through feature selection is compared with the stable subset derived from feature importance methods, allowing us to identify the most consistent discriminators across complementary approaches.

1.5 Emotions and cardiogram-based features

Our previous findings indicate that variability in emotional states challenges the model to generalize effectively [2]. In this context, generalization refers to the model ability to apply patterns learned under one emotional state to another, an ability that tends to deteriorate when affective conditions differ, thereby reducing identification performance.

To examine this effect, we conducted statistical analyses comparing features extracted from baseline and anger segments to identify those significantly affected by emotional changes. Firstly, the Shapiro-Wilk test was applied to each feature within the baseline and anger groups to assess for normal distribution. Depending on the outcome, either a parametric test (independent t-test) or a non-parametric test (Mann-Whitney U test) was employed to evaluate group differences. To control for multiple comparisons, p -values were adjusted using the Bonferroni correction. Effect sizes were calculated in parallel: Cohen's d for the independent t-test, and Cliff's δ for the Mann-Whitney U test, providing an estimate of practical relevance alongside statistical significance. Cliff's δ was calculated using the Python implementation available in the *cliffsDelta* repository on GitHub [39]. Features with adjusted p -values below the significance threshold ($p < 0.05$) were considered significantly influenced by emotional changes.

Due to multicollinearity, we also examine whether highly correlated pairs of features can yield opposite statistical outcomes, for example, one feature showing a significant baseline–anger difference while its counterpart did not. Identifying such pairs helps pinpoint potential pitfalls because it may reveal a big issue in the development of emotion-agnostic biometric systems.

To further investigate the predictive implications of these findings, we evaluated how emotional variability impacts model performance, specifically identification accuracy. Given that the dataset includes two segments corresponding to different emotional states, the RF model was first trained on one segment using all available features and validated through stratified 3-fold cross-validation. Generalization was then assessed by evaluating on samples from the other (unseen) segment. The results, reported in terms of accuracy and F1 score, served as benchmark values. The model was subsequently retrained using two

additional feature sets: (i) features that did not differ significantly across emotional states, and (ii) features that did show significant emotion-related variation. Both subsets underwent the same cross-validation and generalization procedures. These complementary analyses allowed us to determine whether excluding emotion-sensitive features yields more stable identification performance, in comparison to the emotion-sensitive subset.

2. Results

Figure A1 reports the Spearman correlation matrix for all extracted features, with statistically significant coefficients marked by asterisks (*). This provides a nonparametric complement to the Pearson analysis in the main text and uses the same significance threshold and multiple testing control described in Methods.

Figure A1. Heatmap of Spearman correlation coefficients between extracted features, with asterisks (*) indicating statistical significance.

Figures A2 and A3 present rankings from Gini importance and permutation importance as horizontal bar charts. For permutation importance, each feature is permuted 100 times; bars show the mean decrease in performance, and error bars indicate the standard deviation across permutations. Figure A3 shows rankings based on SHapley Additive exPlanations, also as horizontal bar charts. Because the task is multinomial and involves many subjects, SHAP values are computed per sample and per class, then averaged within each class to obtain class-level contributions; for compact visualization, we report the class-averaged importance for each feature.

Figure A2. Gini importance

Figure A3. Permutation feature importance

Figure A4. Feature importance based on the SHapley Additive exPlanations (SHAP) values.

Table A2 presents the results of a statistical analysis comparing the distribution of fiducial-based features between emotional states. As all feature distributions deviate from normality, we use the non-parametric Mann–Whitney U test for comparisons between segments, and we report effect sizes using Cliff’s δ together with qualitative interpretations. The table summarizes all extracted features with the corresponding p -values, adjusted p -values for multiple comparisons, effect sizes, effect size interpretations, and significance flags.

Table A2. Between-segment differences for all features with effect sizes (Cliff’s δ), adjusted p -values, and significance flags

Feature	p-value	r-value	Effect size	Adjusted p	Significant
QRS_int	<0.001	-0.085	negligible	<0.001	TRUE
T_int	<0.001	-0.16	small	<0.001	TRUE
QT_int	<0.001	-0.143	negligible	<0.001	TRUE
ST_int	<0.001	-0.13	negligible	<0.001	TRUE
RS_amp	0.131	0.029	negligible	1.000	FALSE
RQ_amp	0.398	0.016	negligible	1.000	FALSE
RT_amp	0.786	0.005	negligible	1.000	FALSE
TT1_amp	<0.001	0.094	negligible	<0.001	TRUE
TT2_amp	0.047	0.038	negligible	1.000	FALSE
QR_slope	0.546	0.012	negligible	1.000	FALSE
RS_slope	0.150	0.028	negligible	1.000	FALSE
TT1_slope	<0.001	0.121	negligible	<0.001	TRUE
TT2_slope	0.124	0.029	negligible	1.000	FALSE
ECGQRScrest	0.504	0.013	negligible	1.000	FALSE
ECGTcrest	0.511	0.013	negligible	1.000	FALSE
BX_int	<0.001	-0.066	negligible	0.018	TRUE
CB_amp	<0.001	0.074	negligible	0.003	TRUE
CX_amp	0.080	0.034	negligible	1.000	FALSE
CB_slope	<0.001	0.073	negligible	0.004	TRUE
CX_slope	0.023	0.044	negligible	0.662	FALSE

RC_int	<0.001	-0.066	negligible	0.016	TRUE
QX_int	<0.001	-0.064	negligible	0.024	TRUE
QB_int	0.110	-0.031	negligible	1.000	FALSE
SX_int	0.007	-0.051	negligible	0.212	FALSE
SB_int	0.386	0.0166	negligible	1.000	FALSE
BT_int	<0.001	-0.124	negligible	<0.001	TRUE
TX_int	0.797	-0.005	negligible	1.000	FALSE
ICGcrest	<0.001	0.087	negligible	<0.001	TRUE
RR	<0.001	0.131	negligible	<0.001	TRUE

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